

Design of an experimental setup for delivering intracortical microstimulation in vivo via Spiking Neural Network

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Abstract—Electroceutical approaches for the treatment of neurological disorders, such as stroke, can take advantage of neuromorphic engineering, to develop devices able to achieve a seamless interaction with the neural system. This paper illustrates the development and test of a hardware-based Spiking Neural Network (SNN) to deliver neural-like stimulation patterns in an open-loop fashion. Neurons in the SNN have been designed by following the Hodgkin-Huxley formalism, with parameters taken from neuroscientific literature. We then built the set-up to deliver the SNN-driven stimulation in vivo. We used deeply anesthetized healthy rats to test the potential effect of the SNN-driven stimulation. We analyzed the neuronal firing activity pre- and post-stimulation in both the primary somatosensory and the rostral forelimb area. Our results showed that the SNN-based neurostimulation was able to increase the spontaneous level of neuronal firing at both monitored locations, as found in the literature only for closed-loop stimulation. This study represents the first step towards translating the use of neuromorphic-based devices into clinical applications.

Clinical Relevance— Stroke represents one of the leading causes of long-term disability and death worldwide. Intracortical microstimulation is an effective approach for restoring lost sensory motor integration by promoting plasticity among the affected brain areas. Stimulation delivered via neuromorphic-based open-loop systems (i.e. neuromorphic prostheses) can pave the way to novel electroceutical strategies for brain repair.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stroke, among acquired brain injuries, represents a major cause of long-term disability and death. About 87% of stroke cases have ischemic origin. Ischemic stroke, a condition characterized by inadequate oxygen and nutrients to the brain tissue, causes rapid structural damage leading to sensorimotor and cognitive impairment. If an ischemic event occurs at the level of the primary motor cortex, as generally happens, there is a progressive loss of information transmission to the spinal cord, thus causing motor dysfunctions and strongly affecting the normal activities of daily living [1].

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Figure 1. Block diagram showing the SNN running on Zynq SoC where the processing part (CPU) is used for setup and data collection of the programmable logic part (FPGA) through AXI protocol. The target is interfaced with a host computer running a GUI to control the SNN and visualize data.

Standard treatment for recovering lost sensorimotor functions is physical therapy. Nevertheless, its efficacy in promoting spared regions reorganization is often limited or incomplete [1], [2]. State-of-the-art approaches for neuroplasticity induction include electrical stimulation techniques (i.e. electroceutical) [3]. Electroceutical therapy consists of delivering electrical stimulation according to either open- or closed-loop paradigms [4]. The purpose of closed-loop stimulation (CLS) is to deliver electrical pulses coordinated with the ongoing brain activity. Activity-dependent stimulation (ADS) is a promising CLS technique. It consists of detecting single-unit action potentials in one region and providing a stimulation pulse at a short time delay in a different region, under the principle of Hebbian plasticity [5], [6]. Conversely, open-loop stimulation (OLS) does not rely on the continuous feedback from the brain and the stimulation follows previously set parameters [7].

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Figure 2. Schematization of the experimental setup for stimulation. Starting from the spontaneous activity generated by a random neuron of the SNN, a spike train is generated. Each time a spike occurs, a 3.3V pulse is sent to the digital input port of the Intan RHS system. This pulse triggers the stimulation process. A command is sent to the headstage from the Intan RHS, which generates a biphasic stimulation pulse for the electrode placed in S1.

Going beyond state-of-the-art approaches, we here propose a novel OLS paradigm based on the natural-like patterns of neuronal activity exhibited by a Spiking Neural Network (SNN). A neuromorphic-based platform (i.e. a neuromorphic prosthesis [8]) has been designed, developed and connected to a 16-channels microelectrode array (MEA) to deliver electrical stimulation pulses based on the biophysically simulated activity generated by the SNN. We tested the novel SNN-based paradigm on healthy anesthetized rats, and we found that the SNN-driven stimulation induced changes on the spontaneous electrophysiological firing.

These first results constitute an important step towards the translation of neuromorphic-driven stimulation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Animals

Healthy adult Long-Evans rats (5 male, weight: 300-400g, age: 4-5 months; Charles River Laboratories, Calco, LC, Italy) were included in the study. All the rats were treated with the SNN-based stimulation while they were deeply anesthetized. The experimental procedures were performed in the Animal Facility of the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), Genova, Italy and were previously approved by the Italian Ministry of Health and Animal Care (Italy: authorization n. 509/2020-PR).

B. Surgical Procedure

Anesthesia was induced by placing the rat inside a vaporizing chamber and injecting gaseous isoflurane (5% @ 1 lpm). The surgical level of anesthesia was reached via administration of ketamine (80-100 mg/kg IP) and xylazine (5-10 mg/kg). The rat was then secured in a stereotaxic frame and all vital parameters were monitored until the end of the procedure. The surgery began by applying lidocaine cream (a topical analgesic) before performing a midline skin incision to expose the skull. Successfully, a laminectomy was performed at the level of the Cisterna Magna to allow the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) to drain. Then, based on stereotaxic

measurements [9], burr holes (3 mm diameter) were performed over the primary somatosensory area (S1) and rostral forelimb area (RFA), respectively at -1.25 , $+4.25$ and $+3.5$, $+2.5$ AP, ML. Lastly, the dura mater was removed from both burr holes to allow insertion of MEAs (MEAs; A4x4-5 mm-100-125-703-A16, NeuroNexus).

C. Spiking Neural Network

The SNN (Spiking Neural Network) was running on a digital hardware platform based on a System on Chip (SoC) featuring both CPU cores and FPGA known as Zynq, here embedded on its midrange evaluation board the Zybo Z7-20.

The implemented neurons were based on previous work [10]: we used the Hodgkin-Huxley formalism [11] with the parameters from the literature [12]. The modelled cortical neurons were Fast Spiking (FS) and Regular Spiking (RS) neurons, stimulated by a noise mimicking synaptic activity based on equations from [13]. The parameters of the synaptic noise were tuned to obtain spontaneous activity between 1Hz and 10Hz. All neurons were independent and stimulated by a different noise.

The different blocks and elements of the system and their connections are shown in Figure 1. The system is interfaced through a Qt based graphical user interface in Python, communicating with the processing system part of the Zynq SoC, itself communicating with FPGA via AXI Lite. Debug and information of the system are sent by UART at a baudrate of 115200. Data from and to the board is handled by USB 2.0 as communication class device. The interface provides a display for neuron spiking activity, tuning of HH model parameters and global system control. The membrane voltage of each neuron is calculated in real-time by the FPGA part of the SoC clocked at 100MHz. The resultant raster plot showing spiking activity of the network over time is sent through UART interface to the host PC. The outputs of the system are either the membrane voltage of neurons as analog signal generated by a DAC and the digital spike train obtained by threshold detection of the neuron action potentials.

Figure 3. Protocol of the experiment. A: identification of the areas of interest by means of a stereotaxic frame. B: placement of the electrode arrays in the rostral forelimb area (RFA) and in the primary somatosensory area (S1). C: timeline of experiments includes 20 minutes of pre-stimulation (PreS) recording, 60 minutes of SNN-based stimulation and 20 minutes of post-stimulation (PoS) recording.

D. Neuroprosthetic Architecture

The overall system of the neuromorphic-based open-loop neuroprostheses consists of four main components:

- Diligent Zybo Z7-20 development board with the implemented SNN;
- Acquisition/Stimulation system (Intan Technologies RHS Stim/Recording controller): a FPGA-based electrophysiology data acquisition system;
- Headstage: (Intan Technologies RHS2116 microchip): a bidirectional electrophysiology interface system consisting of 16 stimulation/amplifier blocks in which the microelectrode array is placed;
- Host PC: a general-purpose computer running Intan’s graphical user interface (GUI) for real-time data visualization and stimulation/recording parameter setting, and the custom GUI to show the SNN activity in real-time.

The electrical pulse was delivered by the Intan RHS system on a preset channel of the MEA (as described below), selected by sending a specific command to the headstage through the GUI as described below. The stimulation was driven by the patterns generated by a random neuron with 10 Hz firing rate selected from the SNN. Then, the spiking activity was converted into a spike train, a Boolean digital signal. Each time a spike of the selected neuron, encoded as a ‘1’ in the spike train occurred, it was used to trigger the next stimulation pulse. The ‘1’ assertion outputs a pulse of 3.3 V from one of the Zybo Z7-20 board pins, which was forwarded to a digital input port of the Intan RHS. The digital input signal served as trigger for the electrical stimulation. Each time the digital input port read 3.3 V (or, more precisely, a digital signal greater than 2.0 V) the Intan RHS sent a command to the headstage to generate an electrical pulse (see Figure 2 and next paragraph for details on the stimulation).

E. Experimental Protocol and Recording/Stimulation paradigms

MEAs were inserted based on stereotaxic coordinates and after blood vasculature pattern analysis. In both RFA and S1 a 16-channels probe was implanted (NeuroNexus A4x4-5 mm-100-703-A16). The S1 probe had an activated electrode site within the array, dropping the impedance of this site to roughly 0.2 M Ω to allow for stimulation.

Concerning the stimulation site, an impedance analysis was performed and a single channel from S1 was selected according to the lowest value (\sim 200-300 k Ω). Each time a spike was generated from the SNN, a pulse was sent from the custom board to the digital input of the Intan RHS to trigger the stimulation. The stimulation pulse was always designed to be a single squared 60 μ A biphasic, cathodal-leading pulse (200 μ s positive, 200 μ s negative).

The experimental protocol consisted of 20 minutes of pre-stimulation (PreS) recording, 60 minutes of stimulation via SNN-generated activity and 20 minutes of post-stimulation (PoS) recording (see Figure 3). Extracellular signals have been continuously sampled at a rate of 25 kHz and 16 bits of depth.

Figure 4. Effect of open-loop stimulation in both RFA and S1. The statistical analysis was performed considering each channel singularly. A1, B1: 6-s raster plots of the activity recorded in RFA and S1 during pre-stimulation phase. A2, B2: 6-s raster plot of the activity recorded in RFA and S1 during the post-stimulation phase. C, D: plot showing the variation of the mean firing rate (MFR, spikes/s) between pre- and post-stimulation in the two areas by animals. E, F: Boxplot of the MFR. The entire dataset was analyzed with no discrimination among animals to obtain an overall understanding about the efficacy of the stimulation. The central white line represents the median. The top and bottom of the boxes are the 25th and 75th percentiles. The whiskers are representative of the 5th and 95th percentiles. The boxplots have been obtained analyzing the entire dataset with no distinction between rats. Solid line *: $p < 0.05$ Mann-Whitney U-test.

F. Data and Statistical Analysis

A custom Matlab (The MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) pipeline was adopted for the data analysis. Data was filtered with a 3rd order Butterworth bandpass filter in the range of 300–3000 Hz, to remove the low frequency component of the signal and high frequency noise [7]. Offline spike detection was performed on filtered recordings employing precision timing spike detection (PTSD) algorithm [14]. The level of neuronal firing was evaluated by computing the mean firing rate (MFR, spikes/s) in the PreS and PoS recordings for all animals.

Statistical analysis was performed in Matlab as well. As data failed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, we used non-parametric tests for the analysis. We carried out the Mann-Whitney U-test to identify differences in the MFR before and after stimulation. P -values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant. All channels of all animals were pooled together for statistical analysis.

III. RESULTS

We evaluated the neural firing of both RFA and S1 in the PreS and PoS phases to analyze potential variations of the MFR introduced by the SNN-based stimulation, as measure of efficacy in inducing an increase of the spiking activity (see Figure 4). The raster plot of a representative animal is reported for both RFA (Fig. 4 A1-A2) and S1 (Fig. 4 B1-B2). We can observe that the level of firing appears less synchronous and more intense in the post versus the pre stimulation condition. Moreover, the level of MFR increases in post stimulation phases for all animals except for #1 in S1 area (Fig. 4 C-D) whose activity resulted particularly strong in the preS condition. The quantitative analysis (Fig. 4 E-F) confirmed what was seen qualitatively by means of the raster plots. Specifically, we found that the stimulation significantly increased the MFR from PreS to the PoS phase in both RFA (32.12 spikes/s – PreS vs: 40.49 spikes/s – PoS $*p < 0.0009$) and S1 (44.09 spikes/s – PreS vs: 50.42 spikes/s – PoS $*p < 0.02$). In conclusion, we can state that the stimulation pattern generated by means of our SNN is effective in increasing the firing activity of both RFA and S1 compared to the pre-stimulation condition.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, we showed the development of a neuromorphic-based open-loop set-up for neuroprosthetic applications. We first designed an SNN, implemented it in hardware, and then we explored the effectiveness of delivering electrical stimulation via the same SNN. Our preliminary results showed that this ‘neural-like’ stimulation was able to augment the firing rate of the stimulated neuronal populations in two brain areas, in a dataset composed of five healthy animals. This result further strengthened our previous findings, which reported on the effectiveness of ADS in increasing the level of firing [7], as it happens here, where, differently, we used an open-loop paradigm. We here hypothesize that a neural biomimetic pattern better entrains the network with respect to stereotyped stimulation. As a result, the population tends to be more prone to respond to the incoming electrical stimuli. This is also in line with recent human studies [15]. Here we also made a step forward towards translation by using a neuromorphic system, likely to be further exploited for implantable neuroprosthetic devices. Notwithstanding, further investigations will be required, such as those related to the optimization of the SNN parameters according to the features of the studied biological neural network.

Overall, these preliminary results demonstrate that our set-up is capable of delivering a reliable open-loop stimulation,

thus paving the way to an innovative neuromorphic-based approach.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The travels for the collaborative work between Italy and France were supported by Università Italo-Francese/Université Franco-Italienne PHC Galileo for the project ‘NEUROHYSTIM’. V.R.C. is supported by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship MoRPHEUS GA no. 101032054, funded by the European Union under the framework programme H2020-EU.1.3.-EXCELLENT SCIENCE.

This work was carried out within the framework of the project “RAISE - Robotics and AI for Socio-economic Empowerment” and has been supported by European Union – NextGenerationEU.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. S. Phipps and C. A. Cronin, “Management of acute ischemic stroke,” *BMJ*, vol. 368, 2020.
- [2] M. Chiappalone and M. Semprini, “Using robots to advance clinical translation in neurorehabilitation,” *Sci. Robot.*, vol. 7, no. 64, Mar. 2022.
- [3] C. E. Lang, K. J. Waddell, J. Barth, C. L. Holleran, M. J. Strube, and M. D. Bland, “Upper Limb Performance in Daily Life Approaches Plateau Around Three to Six Weeks Post-stroke,” *Neurorehabil. Neural Repair*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 903–914, Oct. 2021.
- [4] F. D. Broccard, S. Joshi, J. Wang, and G. Cauwenberghs, “Neuromorphic neural interfaces: from neurophysiological inspiration to biohybrid coupling with nervous systems,” *J. Neural Eng.*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 041002, Aug. 2017.
- [5] D. J. Guggenmos *et al.*, “Restoration of function after brain damage using a neural prosthesis,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, vol. 110, no. 52, pp. 21177–21182, 2013.
- [6] A. Jackson, J. Mavoori, and E. E. Fetzi, “Long-term motor cortex plasticity induced by an electronic neural implant,” *Nature*, vol. 444, no. 7115, pp. 56–60, 2006.
- [7] A. Averna *et al.*, “Differential Effects of Open- and Closed-Loop Intracortical Microstimulation on Firing Patterns of Neurons in Distant Cortical Areas,” *Cereb. Cortex*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 2879–2896, 2020.
- [8] M. Chiappalone *et al.*, “Neuromorphic-Based Neuroprostheses for Brain Rewiring: State-of-the-Art and Perspectives in Neuroengineering,” *Brain Sci.*, vol. 12, no. 11, p. 1578, Nov. 2022.
- [9] J. A. Kleim, R. Bruneau, P. VandenBerg, E. MacDonald, R. Mulrooney, and D. Pocock, “Motor cortex stimulation enhances motor recovery and reduces peri-infarct dysfunction following ischemic insult,” *Neurol. Res.*, vol. 25, no. 8, pp. 789–793, 2003.
- [10] F. Khojratee, F. Grassia, S. Saighi, and T. Levi, “Optimized real-time biomimetic neural network on FPGA for bio-hybridization,” *Front. Neurosci.*, vol. 13, no. APR, pp. 1–17, 2019.
- [11] A. L. Hodgkin and A. F. Huxley, “A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve,” *J. Physiol.*, vol. 117, no. 4, pp. 500–544, Aug. 1952.
- [12] M. Pospischil *et al.*, “Minimal Hodgkin-Huxley type models for different classes of cortical and thalamic neurons,” *Biol. Cybern.*, vol. 99, no. 4–5, pp. 427–441, 2008.
- [13] A. Destexhe, M. Rudolph, J. M. Fellous, and T. J. Sejnowski, “Fluctuating synaptic conductances recreate in vivo-like activity in neocortical neurons,” *Neuroscience*, vol. 107, no. 1, pp. 13–24, 2001.
- [14] A. Maccione, M. Gandolfo, P. Massobrio, A. Novellino, S. Martinoia, and M. Chiappalone, “A novel algorithm for precise identification of spikes in extracellularly recorded neuronal signals,” *J. Neurosci. Methods*, vol. 177, no. 1, pp. 241–249.
- [15] C. Cottone, A. Cancelli, P. Pasqualetti, C. Porcaro, C. Salustri, and F. Tecchio, “A New, High-Efficacy, Noninvasive Transcranial Electric Stimulation Tuned to Local Neurodynamics,” *J. Neurosci.*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 586–594, Jan. 2018.